

Privacy in the Age of Smartphone: A Study of Iranian Users' Standards and Habits

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Abstract: Recent surveys show that the number of smartphone and tablet users has been increasing sharply in the Middle-East and Iranian users are believed to be one of the most technology savvy nations in the region. In fact, youth is the largest population bloc in Iran and officials have indicated there is a high tendency to use the latest technologies and live with high-tech standards among them. For example, recently and in an unprecedented event, there was a huge queue for the LG G2 handset release in Iran. Nevertheless, studies have shown that the level of ICT education, specifically among the general public, is below the western countries standards and the increasing penetration of IT in the Iranian traditional society has become the source of many problems in the recent years. Moreover, due to certain political conflicts and sanctions against Iran, major IT companies such as Google and Apple are not providing their products and services in Iran and hence, they do not provide any support or assistance to this set of users. Therefore, with the help of the government, Iranian companies have started to manufacture smartphone and tablets. However, all of these devices have the Android operating system and, being a newly shaped business, the quality of these handsets is not yet comparable to internationally renowned providers.

Keywords: Privacy, Smartphone, Apple Jailbreak, Android Rooting, ICT in Iran.